

building-integrated user-
empowered flexibility trading

Deliverable D8.2: Dissemination and communication action plans and target KPIs

WP8 – Dissemination and Communication

March 31, 2025

PUBLIC

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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the dissemination and communication action plans to identify the project's key outcomes to be communicated and the relevant stakeholders to whom these key messages should be addressed, to encourage them to interface with the project, and to learn and contribute to the obtained results. This to enhance the exploitation and take-up of BlueBird's results.

Furthermore, an overview is provided of the main tools and channels (website, social media, press releases, scientific publications, videos, etc.) that will be used to reach these stakeholders, an overview of the timing of public deliverables and milestones that will drive the communication actions and a monitoring strategy with KPIs to follow-up the effectiveness of the actions taken.

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Acronyms and Definitions

Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BIM	Building Information Modelling
DR	Demand Response
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EC	Energy Community
ESCO	Energy Service Company
EV	Electric Vehicle
GUI	Graphic User Interface
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MS	Milestone
RES	Renewable Energy Source
SAREF	Smart Applications REference ontology
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator
TSO	Transmission System Operator
WP	Work Package

I. INTRODUCTION

I.1. Purpose and organization of the document

This deliverable describes the communication and dissemination strategy to identify the project's key messages to be communicated (section III), the identification of the relevant stakeholders to whom these key messages should be addressed (section V), and the main tools and channels that will be used to reach these stakeholders (sections VI).

Furthermore, an overview is provided on the branding of the project (section VII) and the defined KPIs and monitoring strategy to follow-up the project's dissemination and communication actions (section VIII).

The results from the communication and dissemination activities will be reported in *D8.3 - 1st report on dissemination, communication and clustering activities and results* (M18) and *D8.4 - 2nd report on dissemination, communication and clustering activities and results* (M36) .

I.2. Scope and audience

The communication and dissemination activities of WP8 support the activities of *WP7 – Regulatory framework, project impact, and go-to-market strategies* to realize a maximal exploitation and valorisation of the solutions developed within BlueBird. This deliverable is thus intended for WP7 partners as well as for the EC project officer in order to follow-up on the project's dissemination and communication activities.

II. OVERALL OBJECTIVES AND KEY CONCEPTS

The BlueBird project aims to provide and demonstrate a set of multi-carrier flexibility services for buildings and to empower the building's end users to follow-up and set their flexibility conditions and preferences. Therefore a number of services and interfaces will be designed to valorize the available flexibility in a building, and a toolbox containing modules for a.o. energy efficiency recommendations, load profile classification and forecasting, load flexibility analysis and modelling, consumption & RES forecasting, etc.

Furthermore a microservices based reference architecture will be delivered, which will allow to easily select and deploy components from the toolbox for a specific building and use case, on top of existing energy control systems. This selection and deployment will be further supported by BlueBird's innovative component orchestration GUI which will allow to easily define the functionalities and workflow of a particular use case. Integration with existing flexible assets, buildings systems, measurement devices and diverse other data sets (e.g. weather services, static building data, user feedback, etc.) will be realized by designing a number of data interoperability modules. All these heterogeneous data sources will be mapped onto a common semantic data model based on existing standards (a.o. SAREF, BIM) to improve interoperability.

The designed solutions will be evaluated in 7 demonstrators in 5 EU countries, comprising different types of buildings and value chains, spanning more than 30 buildings. At least 24 use cases will be demonstrated in those pilot sites, including a.o. data interoperability, value stacking with building flexibility assets, DR event management, smart EV charging considering local RES availability, optimal usage of storage systems, occupancy control, investment decision support, etc. For every demonstrator site, the impact of BlueBird's solutions on the buildings' SRI will be evaluated, measuring the ability of buildings to accommodate occupant needs, energy grid needs, and maintaining energy efficiency and building operation.

The replication potential of the solutions will be tested in more than 300 buildings during the project. A Replicability Package will be designed and demonstrated consisting of:

- The microservices toolbox.
- A set of guidelines for using the toolbox to measure and improve the energy efficiency of a building, unlock additional flexibility, improve end user empowerment and smart solutions adoption.
- A building typology map to match a given building's type with the most convenient services provided by the project.
- A set of transparent business models, feasibility studies and value networks to maximize the adoption of the project solutions and improve buildings flexibility.

WP8 is responsible for the design and deployment of a comprehensive and well-structured communication and dissemination strategy to ensure a broad promotion of the BlueBird concepts, developed solutions and (pilot) results to all relevant stakeholders and support WP7 to maximize the valorization of BlueBird's results.

II.1. Communication objectives

The communication objectives are threefold:

1. Provide the right tools, channels and messages to reach the relevant stakeholders.
2. Ensure that relationships with those stakeholders work in both directions: spreading of information and project outcomes from the consortium but also capturing feedback from the audiences to further steer the research and developments.
3. Ensure a broad visibility and awareness about the main BlueBird project results.

The different communication channels to achieve these objectives are detailed in section VI.

II.2. Dissemination objectives

The dissemination objectives are also threefold:

- **Reach, stimulate, and engage a critical mass** of relevant stakeholders by large-scale dissemination campaigns to ensure that the BlueBird results are well-known and taken up.
- **Foster impactful contributions** from potential early adopters aligned with planned exploitation plans and project outcomes.
- **Increase trust** among industrial professionals and related stakeholders in data and AI-based solutions promoting European acceptance and utilization of project outputs for continued innovation beyond BlueBird.

These objectives will be realized via different types of dissemination activities:

- **Public Dissemination** via the communication channels presented in section VI to all target audiences.
- **Journal and Conference Publications:** scientific project results will be published in peer reviewed, highly ranked international scientific journals and conferences (see section VI.6.).
- **Industrial sector-oriented activities:** The consortium will actively participate to the strengthening of the digital transformation of the buildings sector and will establish synergies with European Associations e.g., [BRIDGE](#), [European Digital Innovation Hubs](#), [New European Bauhaus](#), [Built4People](#), [Energy-efficient Buildings \(EeB\)](#), [smartEN](#), [2Zero](#), [DUT partnership](#), the [European Partnership for Energy and the Environment \(EPEE\)](#) and the [Clean Energy Transition Partnership](#), project clusters and and other European initiatives such as projects funded under related calls and other EU projects working on climate-neutral economy, sustainable industry, smart energy, and smart cities areas.

The dissemination activities will be closely monitored via a number of KPIs, as outlined in section VIII.

II.3. Engagement with EU level stakeholders and liaisons with EU initiatives

BlueBird aims to align its tools with existing standards and regulations, fostering a supportive regulatory and market environment to decarbonize the built environment while encouraging the replication and deployment of the developed models and solutions across the EU. The goal of this task is to engage with stakeholders at the EU level in the building and energy sector ecosystems to demonstrate the technical, social, and economic benefits of BlueBird’s tools and services.

To achieve this, targeted communication efforts will be directed toward EU policy makers, industry associations, sustainable finance institutions, and other relevant actors. Additionally, expert meetings and stakeholder events will be organized to present and discuss project outcomes, supporting the development and implementation of EU policies on the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI), smart buildings, and grid interaction.

Partners will also participate in cross-fertilization activities at the EU level, such as those suggested by BRIDGE, to collaborate and exchange insights with relevant research projects. Moreover, they will actively participate in EU-level policy discussions, stakeholder events, international conferences, and professional networks.

As a first action, BlueBird joined the [Smart Energy Cluster](#), a collaboration of more than 20 ongoing EU projects focused on merging different energy services and incorporating non-energy benefits whilst overcoming market fragmentation and fostering cooperation. This initiative wants to bridge gaps and create a common ground for business development across different segments. The main goals are to:

- Communicate the projects' activities and success stories to groups interested in smart energy solutions.
- Amplify the impact of innovative service offerings, reduced energy costs for end users.
- Achieve faster payback periods for sustainable energy investments.

Furthermore, BlueBird has established a [community in Zenodo](#) as a centralized, open-access repository for project outputs in order to contribute to the project's dissemination and communication action plan. The Zenodo community serves as a digital archive for all BlueBird related publications, datasets, software, presentations, and reports, ensuring long-term preservation and accessibility of research outputs to stakeholders, researchers, and the overall public:

1. Compliance with Open Science and FAIR Principles: Supports the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) data principles by making research outputs citable and shareable with DOIs, aligning with the EU's Open Science policies.
2. Wider Outreach and Engagement: Acts as a communication tool by allowing project partners to share results with policy-makers, industry experts, educators, and the general public. Increases visibility by integrating with OpenAIRE, Google Scholar, and other indexing services.
3. Facilitating Collaboration and Knowledge Sharing: The community provides a platform for interaction between researchers, helping to exchange knowledge and foster new collaborations.
4. Impact Assessment and Reporting: Helps in tracking impact metrics such as downloads, citations, and views, which can be used in project reporting and impact assessment. In addition, it supports Horizon Europe by demonstrating compliance with dissemination obligations.

Other initial actions include the participation in the BRIDGE General Assembly on March 25-26 2025 in Brussels.

Figure 1. Participation of BlueBird in the BRIDGE General Assembly 2025.

II.4. Individual Dissemination Plans

BlueBird is carried out by an interdisciplinary consortium of experienced and complementary partners from five European countries, each bringing their own expertise and background. The dissemination of project results will be undertaken by all partners within their respective professional networks:

- **Energy sector services stakeholders** - including owners and managers of critical infrastructure (WeSmart, Karno Energy, ENEA, ENK, EWH) and energy sector stakeholders (TERSA) - will share the project outcomes within their areas of activity. They will engage with relevant sector associations (e.g., [Industry4Europe](#), [EHPA](#), [EUREC](#), [SolarPower Europe](#), [European Energy Forum](#), [SmartEN](#)) and participate in sustainable industry-focused events. Through demonstrations they will bring together key stakeholders to advise on cost-effective decarbonization strategies for the energy sector using emerging European enabling technologies.
- **Public authorities** (AMB, PSNC) will disseminate project findings within their organisations to showcase best practices for sustainability through digitalization. Additionally, they will participate in regulatory meetings and events to share the lessons learned from the project.
- **Leading research institutions on technical development** (CIMNE, imec, DTU, USTUTT, AIT) and **on sociological and users' engagement research** (SEEBG) will publish their findings in international peer-reviewed scientific journals and present them at international conferences. They will also incorporate project insights into lectures and training programs for early-career researchers (master students, PhDs, postdoctoral researchers). Furthermore, they will take part in workshops and conferences to engage with other academic institutions, researchers and other projects' stakeholders, facilitating the exchange of knowledge and best practices.
- **Ecosystem entities and associations** (BPIE) will disseminate project outcomes to stakeholders within the European sustainable built environment ecosystem. They will also engage with EU institutions, policy makers, multiplier networks, professional associations, NGOs, sustainable finance organisations and other relevant actors.
- **IT industrial partners** (Inetum) will implement internal dissemination actions targeting business units to strengthen knowledge transfer between the R&D department and operational teams. This will be complemented by showcasing the project at events and trade fairs focused on innovative sustainability technologies.

III. MAIN PROJECT OUTCOMES

Throughout the project, BlueBird will generate various results that should effectively reach the identified target audience groups (see section V) to maximize impact and adoption potential. To achieve this, the developed tools, interfaces, data models, pilot validations, and more will be promoted through diverse and targeted communication and dissemination actions (see section VI).

The primary outcomes of BlueBird that will be highlighted and promoted include:

- **A comprehensive, validated toolset, and associated micro services based reference architecture:** this will enable the effective use of buildings as energy flexibility assets that can seamlessly integrate into the systems of energy market players (such as TSOs, DSOs, and flex aggregators) while maximally aligning with the needs and acceptance criteria of end users (building managers, occupants).
- **Modular, plug-and-play components:** The toolset will consist of independent, containerized, plug-and-play components that can be combined to address various use case tasks. These components will be portable, reusable, and adaptable for deployment both at the edge and in the cloud. This flexibility facilitates the easy adaptation of solutions to different building configurations, maximizing replicability. An component orchestration GUI will simplify the selection of the necessary components for specific use cases, as well as the definition and deployment of associated workflows.
- **Multi-carrier flexibility services and user-centric tools:** The toolbox will include digital twin models, forecasting and control algorithms, tools to assess and quantify consumer response to flexibility services, and transparent GUIs. These GUIs will allow users to manage flexibility settings, understand the reasoning behind proposed flexibility actions, and enhance user empowerment for flexibility services.
- **A common semantic data model for interoperability:** Built on existing standards, this data model and associated data interoperability modules will ensure seamless integration of the BlueBird toolbox with current building systems, flexible assets, measurement devices, existing datasets and services.
- **Validation and demonstration across 7 pilot sites:** the solutions will be tested in diverse building types, for at least 24 novel use cases, including an associated smart readiness analysis for the involved buildings.
- **A comprehensive Replicability Package:** This package will include a microservices catalogue, guidelines for evaluating energy efficiency improvements and available flexibility, validated business models and value networks, and a building typology map to match building types with the most relevant microservices.

These results will be reported continuously throughout the project's duration, coinciding with the completion of deliverables and milestones (see section IV).

IV. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION TIMELINE

To maximize the widespread adoption of the results of the project, we focus on the specification and implementation of open solutions. Consequently, most deliverables will be publicly released. The release of a deliverable or reaching a project milestone will be followed by appropriate communication and dissemination actions to inform the intended target audiences.

Table 1 and Table 2 below give an overview of the public deliverables and project milestones with due dates, lead beneficiaries and supporting beneficiaries.

Table 1 – BlueBird public deliverables

Nº	Deliverable title	Due date	Lead Beneficiary	Supporting Beneficiaries
D1.1	Collaborative Working Environment and its Maintenance	M2	INETUM	CIMNE
D8.1	Communication Materials and Website	M3	IMEC	
D8.2	Dissemination and Communication Actions Plans and Target KPIs	M3	IMEC	BPIE
D6.1	Privacy- and Security- by Design BlueBird Big Data Reference Architecture	M9	CIMNE	INETUM
D2.1	KPIs, Implementation Plan and Demo Implementation of SRI	M14	USTUTT	KARNO, WESMART, AMB, ENEA, ENK, EWH, PSNC
D3.1	Description of the Preliminary Multi-Carrier Flexibility Services for Buildings	M15	DTU	INETUM, CIMNE, IMEC, PSNC, USTUTT, UPC
D4.1	Report Identifying Main Motivators and Barriers to Flexibility and Smart Technology Adoption Based on COM-B	M15	SEEBG	USTUTT
D5.1	Description of the Preliminary Flexibility Trade-off Services	M15	PSNC	INETUM, CIMNE, ENK, DTU

D6.2	Technical Description of the Preliminary BlueBird Supportive Platform	M15	CIMNE	INETUM
D7.1	Report on Regulatory Background for Smart Grid-Ready Buildings and the Energy Network	M15	BPIE	AIT
D2.2	Report on the First Demonstrations Evaluation Results	M18	USTUTT	KARNO, WESMART, AMB, ENEA, ENK, EWH, PSNC
D4.2	Preliminary Guidelines on Tailoring System Functionalities, User Interfaces, and Engagement Strategies to Meet User Needs and Preferences Effectively	M18	SEEBG	INETUM, USTUTT
D8.3	1 st Report on Dissemination, Communication and Clustering Activities and Results	M18	IMEC	BPIE
D7.3	Preliminary Analysis of the Project Impact	M22	BPIE	AIT
D2.3	Report on the Intermediate Demonstrations Evaluation Results	M26	USTUTT	KARNO, WESMART, AMB, ENEA, ENK, EWH, PSNC
D3.2	Description of the Final Multi-Carrier Flexibility Services for Buildings	M30	DTU	INETUM, CIMNE, IMEC, PSNC, USTUTT, UPC
D5.2	Description of the Final Flexibility Trade-off Services	M30	PSNC	INETUM, CIMNE, ENK, DTU
D6.3	Technical Description of the Final BlueBird Supportive Platform	M30	CIMNE	INETUM
D7.5	Market Integration, Cost-Benefit Analysis, and Business Models	M30	AIT	BPIE
D4.3	Final Guidelines on Tailoring System Functionalities, User Interfaces, and Engagement Strategies to Meet User Needs and Preferences Effectively	M32	SEEBG	INETUM, USTUTT
D2.4	Report on the Final Demonstration's Evaluation Results	M36	USTUTT	KARNO, WESMART, AMB, ENEA, ENK, EWH, PSNC

D7.6	Report & Fact Sheets on Project Impact, and Good Practices with Replication Potential	M36	BPIE	AIT
D8.4	2 nd Report on Dissemination, Communication and Clustering Activities and Results	M36	IMEC	BPIE

Table 2 - Overview of BlueBird Milestones

Nº	Milestone Name	Due Date	Lead Beneficiary	Supporting Beneficiaries
MS1	Propject kick-off	M1	CIMNE	INETUM
MS2	Marketing Material and Website Available	M3	IMEC	CIMNE, INETUM
MS3	Demonstration Implementation Plan	M7	USTUTT	KARNO, WESMART, AMB, ENEA, ENK, EWH, PSNC
MS4	1 st Social Science Input to Use Case Definition of Flex Systems	M12	SEEBG	
MS5	Release of the V1 of Technical Components for Deployment	M12	DTU	SEEBG, PSNC
MS6	Start of Demos with V1 Components	M15	CIMNE	USTUTT
MS7	First Demonstrations Evaluation Results Available	M18	USTUTT	KARNO, WESMART, AMB, ENEA, ENK, EWH, PSNC
MS8	Preliminary Analysis of the Project Impact	M22	BPIE	
MS9	Final Release of Technical Components and their Deployment	M28	DTU	SEEBG, PSNC
MS10	Start of Demos with Final Components	M30	CIMNE	USTUTT

MS11	Final Pilots' Results Evaluation	M34	USTUTT	KARNO, WESMART, AMB, ENEA, ENK, EWH, PSNC
MS12	Final Project Impact Analysis	M36	BPIE	
MS13	Replicability Package and Sustainability Plan	M36	BPIE	
MS14	Final Public Outreach	M36	IMEC	CIMNE, INETUM

V. TARGET AUDIENCE AND KEY STAKEHOLDERS

The following stakeholder groups are identified as the main audiences we want to reach with our communication and dissemination activities, to present them the solutions that will be developed, validated and demonstrated in the project:

- **TA1 - Users:** Energy and non-energy sector players providing energy and non-energy services. Mainly, energy retailers, energy aggregators, DSOs, ESCos, managers of energy communities (ECs), district network managers, real estate developers, urban planners, that must have a special focus on energy efficiency and flexibility.
- **TA2 - End users:** The end users, including dwelling and buildings occupants, community and neighbourhood organizations, EV owners, energy prosumers, as main originators of energy consumption and owners of distributed energy generation sites, involved via flexibility or sufficiency strategies.
- **TA3 - Enablers:** EU and national level institutions, governments and policy makers that can create an enable regulatory and market environments. Policy makers at all levels:
 - Local and regional authorities' organizations and public buildings management agencies
 - National ministries
 - European Associations and Partnerships (Built4People, DUT, AEEBC, IEA-EBC, etc.)
 - Standard Development Organizations and regulators (ETSI, CEN-CENELEC, etc.)
 - Building data stock managers (EU BSO currently developed by BPIE)
 - EU level professional associations and multiplier networks (BRIDGE, ECTP - Build4People, Efficient Buildings Community).
- **TA4 – Technology and energy suppliers:** Those who bring the technical context to integrate BlueBird in the market e.g., Building Energy Management System (BEMS) providers, HVAC providers, IoT devices manufacturers, charging stations providers and operators, cloud providers, systems integrators, etc.
- **TA5 - Researchers:** Experts in AI, in data science, in consumer engagement, in UX, in buildings energy efficiency, in urban-district planning, both academic and industrial.
- **TA6 - General Public:** National and international stakeholders beyond the direct target audiences who have general information and transparency rights e.g. environmental agencies, etc.

VI. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION CHANNELS

Below an overview is provided of the main communication and dissemination channels that will be used to spread the results of the project to the relevant stakeholders.

To track all the communication and dissemination activities within the project, a dissemination tracker excel file was created, shared on the project’s Sharepoint and distributed within the consortium.

Responsible Partner	Date	Type of online dissemination	Post Title / Description	Link	Comments
SEEBURG	24/01/2025	Post on social media account	Project overview	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7288509280587030528/	
WESMART	26/11/2024	Post on website	Project overview	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7288118639386333184-r	
CIMNE	24/01/2025	Post on social media account	CIMNE is proud to host the kick-off meeting for the Blue Bird	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/cimne-greendeal-cimne-bluebirdproject-activity:7288118639386333184-r	
CIMNE	01/11/2024	Post on website	BlueBird project sheet on portfolio	https://besgroup.cimne.com/portfolio/bluebird-building-integrated-user-empowered-flexibility-trading/	
IMEC	13/02/2025	Post on social media account	Post on project LinkedIn page on kick-off of the project	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7295724720312733696/	

Figure 2. BlueBird Dissemination Tracker

Furthermore, as mentioned in section II.3. a [community in Zenodo](#) has been established, as an open-access digital archive for all BlueBird related publications, datasets, software modules, presentations, reports, etc.

VI.1. BlueBird Website

The public project website is available on <https://bluebird-project.eu> and will be one of the main communication tools throughout the project. The website will provide an overview of the main project’s objectives and expected outcomes, the consortium partners, the 7 pilot demonstrators, and an overview of upcoming and past events where the project or its results will be/were presented or demonstrated. The project website will also contain an overview of downloadable materials, such as project publications, press releases and public deliverables.

At least one blog post or news update per month will be posted on the website during the project lifetime. Imec will build and manage the website, but through a rotation system, all partners will be asked to occasionally prepare content, such as writing news articles (based a.o. on deliverable deadlines, publications, participation in events, etc.) and preparing social media content, which will then be published on the website and on the LinkedIn project page by imec.

All partners will use their communication channels in order to generate traffic to the BlueBird website and increase the visibility of the project.

Figure 3. BlueBird website

VI.2. Social Media

Social media will be used to raise awareness on project results, pilot validations, project events and publications. We will use LinkedIn as main social media channel as it gives the opportunity of enhancing two-way communication with well-defined professional groups of stakeholders.

The news items that will be posted on the website will also be published on the project LinkedIn page and reposted by the different project partners within their own LinkedIn networks.

Similar to the website, imec will coordinate the publication of posts on LinkedIn, using the provided inputs by all project partners. A first post on the kick-off of the project was published in February and a second one end of March in response to the participation of BlueBird in the BRIDGE General Assembly 2025.

Figure 4. Screenshot of the BlueBird LinkedIn page and first post.

VI.3. Newsletters / Press Releases

An electronic project newsletter or newsletter will be released every 6 months, providing updated information and highlights for the stakeholders, including the announcement of conferences, presentations or publications.

Imec will coordinate the writing of these newsletters, contacting project partners to provide input based on recent releases of deliverables, publications, participation in events, etc.

A first press release was drafted by CIMNE after the project's kick-off meeting in January and published on a few project partners' websites, e.g. for the [University of Stuttgart](#).

VI.4. Flyers & Posters

3 flyers and posters will be created throughout the project to communicate the main goals and outcomes from the project to the relevant stakeholders, on scientific and industrial conferences, workshops, fairs and other types of events. Imec will take the lead for designing these, using inputs from the whole consortium.

A first flyer highlighting the project context and key objectives, the different partners, and the 7 pilot environments has been created and will be used in the first events in which BlueBird will participate, such as the BRIDGE General Assembly.

BlueBird Context

To achieve the EU's Green Deal and sustainability targets, its power grid has seen a drastic increase renewable energy resources. This causes balancing the electricity supply and demand to be ever more challenging and calls for increased flexibility in the electricity system. Hence, flexibility schemes lie at the core of the EU's holy grail to realize the required energy transition.

BlueBird focuses on unlocking such energy flexibility from buildings, and thus will deliver a comprehensive and validated toolset, to fully allow competitive adoption of buildings as energy flexibility assets. BlueBird's toolset will build on standard ontologies to supporting a smooth integration of services towards energy market players (i.e. TSO, DSO, aggregators) while maximally aligning with end-user's (i.e., building managers, occupants) requirements and acceptance criteria.

BlueBird Objectives

The project has 5 key objectives:

- Provide multi-carrier flexibility services for buildings, integrating energy and non-energy carriers, empowering end-users with control;
- Facilitate the flexibility trading between buildings and the energy market stakeholders;
- Evaluate BlueBird in 7 demonstrators with residential, public, commercial, office and industrial buildings;
- Maximize adoption based on (1) business models and successful value networks, and (2) a set of feasibility studies for on-site storage and renewables;
- Deliver a highly replicable, standardized, benefit-demonstrated Replicability Package.

Partners

For more information, please follow us on

[linkedin.com/company/bluebird-project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/bluebird-project)

bluebird-project.eu

The BlueBird project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101192462.

BlueBird Business Cases

BlueBird has defined a wide range of targeted high-level services that form the core drivers for the technical developments. These services have been identified through a detailed analysis of 7 business cases across Europe, covering 24 use cases. Below, we summarize the business cases in terms of the available equipment, involved stakeholders, and how flexibility will be used.

To realize these services, BlueBird will deliver a toolset of hierarchical predictive control software, comprising a Trading Manager (to unlock flexibility and allow participation in energy markets), a Flexibility Manager (to jointly control assets at the building level), and interaction tools (to empower users and building managers).

#1 Karno

Karno (a Belgian zero-carbon district heating developer) will upgrade its 4th generation low-temperature (35°C) network to improve integration in the electrical power grid. This includes (1) increasing flexibility by adapting to user behavior, (2) leveraging additional flex from storage and local PV, and (3) expanding the heating network.

#2 AMB

The metropolitan area of Barcelona (AMB) aims to leverage flexibility from public building systems (heat pumps for heating and/or cooling, gas-based heating) and EV chargers, to (1) optimize self-consumption of local PV and solar thermal, and/or (2) enable participation to the Iberian electricity markets (e.g. TOU-based).

#3 WeSmart

As an energy aggregator, WeSmart wants to leverage EMS-based control within the energy community at the Tour & Taxis site in Brussels, Belgium. This will encompass (1) real-time data acquisition from end users' smart meters, EV chargers and 10k rooftop PV panels, (2) recommendation-based DR from end users, and (3) validating economic viability accounting for user behavior.

#4 Enea Office

The Polish power company Enea will enable dynamic management of its office building's cooling and heating system, fed by a municipal heating grid. This will encompass (1) predictive monitoring and control of the office's and social rooms' thermostats, and (2) providing users with thermostat settings accounting for their comfort.

#5 Enea Grid

As a 2nd case for Enea, it will maximally exploit flexibility of a high/medium voltage power station's cooling and heating, with minimal impact on comfort and assuring safety of technical staff. BlueBird will realize (1) non-intrusive monitoring and AI-based predictive control, and (2) dynamic heating and cooling management to unlock flexibility.

#6 EK

The Austrian flexibility aggregator and service provider Energie Kompass will market Wasserverband Südtirols Burgenland's water works building's battery and operational flex. This will entail (1) upgrading the automation system of the water tanks, (2) optimizing its operation and scheduling exploiting the tanks as energy storage, and (3) improving VPP capability and functionality.

#7 EWH

EWH, as a vertically integrated electricity supplier/DSO, generates electricity from local renewables and manages supply. EWH will exploit BlueBird technology to better manage its largest customers (i.e., hotels) to (1) identify and forecast their load and flexibility, and subsequently, (2) turn the hotels into smart-grid-ready buildings.

Figure 5. First BlueBird flyer

VI.5. Videos

At least 3 project videos will be created to communicate the principal messages from the project to the stakeholders. These videos will be disseminated via the project's website and LinkedIn page and will be used when presenting the project on events, workshops, fairs, etc.

VI.6. Scientific Publications

The dissemination of the scientific project outcomes will be achieved thanks to papers and publications released in international scientific journals and proceedings of conferences.

Articles will be published regularly in peer-reviewed journals of high standard along with the course of the project. A list of relevant scientific journals and conferences targeted by the consortium has been identified (see table below), which will be contacted for the dissemination of the project activities and outcomes.

This list will be continuously updated with new publication opportunities.

Table 3 - Journals and conferences

Journal/ Conference	Description	Date/ Periodicity/ Location	Publisher/ Organizer
Building and Environment https://www.journals.elsevier.com/building-and-environment	International journal on aspects related to building science, urban physics, and human interaction with the indoor and outdoor built environment	Monthly	Elsevier
Automation in Construction https://www.journals.elsevier.com/automation-in-construction	International journal on aspects related to Information Technologies in Design, Engineering, Construction Technologies, and Maintenance and Management of Constructed Facilities.	Monthly	Elsevier
Energy and Buildings https://www.journals.elsevier.com/energy-and-buildings	International journal devoted to investigations of energy use and efficiency in buildings.	Twice a month (1st and 15th of each month)	Elsevier
IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid https://ieeepes.org/publications/transactions-on-smart-grid/	Cross disciplinary journal on aspects related to research on and development of the smart grid.	Bimonthly	IEEE
ACM e-Energy (International Conference on Future Energy Systems) https://energy.acm.org/conferences/eenergy/2025/index.php	International conference computing and communication for smart energy systems and energy-efficient computing and communication systems.	Yearly, next edition: June 17-20, 2025 Rotterdam (The Netherlands)	ACM
ACM Buildsys (International Conference on Systems for Energy-Efficient Buildings, Cities and Transportation) https://buildsys.acm.org/	International conference on energy-efficient buildings, cities, and transportation driven by networked sensing, computing, and control functions.	Yearly	ACM
International Conference on Energy Economics and Energy Policies (ICEEEP) https://www.iceeep.com/index.html	Worldwide Scientific oriented congress on energy economics and policies.	Yearly in April	ICEEEP

Metrology for Living Environment https://www.metroenv.org/	International workshop: several topics through “Special sessions”, or special session proposal.	Yearly in June	IEEE
IEEE Transactions on Energy Markets, Policy & Regulation https://ieeepes.org/publications/transactions-on-energy-markets-policy-and-regulation/	Top tier journal on energy markets	4 issues per year	IEEE
Power Systems Computation Conference (PSCC) https://psc2026.cy/	Flagship European Conference on Power Systems	Every 2 years	Elsevier
PowerTech Conference https://2025.ieee-powertech.org/	Flagship European Conference on Power Systems	Every 2 years	IEEE
Energy and AI	Open access journal on innovative applications of AI addressing the critical challenges in energy systems, materials, chemistry, energy utilization & conversion, energy & society, decarbonization and sustainable development, data-driven optimization algorithms, and AI ethics.	4 issues per year	Elsevier
Journal of Building Engineering https://www.journals.elsevier.com/journal-of-building-engineering	Interdisciplinary journal on aspects related to the whole life cycle of the built environment; from the design phase through to construction, operation, performance, maintenance and its deterioration.	Monthly	Elsevier
ECPPM conference (European Conference on Product and Process Modeling) https://www.ecppm.org/	International conference on BIM and ICT applications in the AEC/FM (Architecture, Engineering, Construction and Facilities Management) domains.	Biannual, next edition in 2026	European Association of Product and Process Modelling (EAPPM)
European Conference on Computing in Construction (EC3) https://ec-3.org/conference2025/	International conference on information, communication and technological research, innovation and policy for the construction sector as a whole.	Yearly, next edition: 14-17/07/2025 – Porto (Portugal)	European Council for Computing in Construction
SEB (International Conference on Sustainability in Energy and Buildings) http://seb-25.kesinternational.org/	International conference on energy in buildings, neighbourhoods and cities from a theoretical, practical, implementation and simulation perspective.	Yearly, next edition: 17-19/09/2021 – Catania (Italy)	KES International
IEECB&SC conference (International Conference on Improving Energy Efficiency in Commercial Buildings and Smart Communities) https://e3p.jrc.ec.europa.eu/events/12th-international-conference-improving-energy-efficiency-commercial-buildings-and-smart	International conference focused on energy efficiency in new and existing non-residential buildings.	Biannual	European Commission
Sustainability https://www.mdpi.com/journal/sustainability	International open access journal on environmental, cultural,	Semimonthly	MDPI

	economic, and social sustainability of human beings.		
ISGT Europe https://iee-isgt-europe.org/	International conference on smart grid and related technologies.	Yearly, next edition: 20 - 23/10/2025 – Malta	IEEE PES
IEEE SmartGridComm (International Conference on Communications, Control, and Computing Technologies for Smart Grids) https://sgc2025.ieee-smartgridcomm.org/	International conference on communications, energy, control, signal processing, analytics and information systems related to smart grids.	Yearly, next edition: 29/9 - 2/10/2025 – Toronto (Canada)	IEEE Comsoc
Applied Energy https://www.journals.elsevier.com/applied-energy	Journal on innovation, research, development and demonstration in the areas of energy conversion and conservation, the optimal use of energy resources, analysis and optimization of energy processes, mitigation of environmental pollutants, and sustainable energy.	Twice a month	Elsevier
Renewable Energy https://www.journals.elsevier.com/renewable-energy	Journal on various topics and technologies of renewable energy systems and components.	18 times per year	Elsevier
Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks https://www.journals.elsevier.com/sustainable-energy-grids-and-networks	Journal on theoretical and applied research dealing with energy, information grids and power networks, including smart grids from super to micro grid scales.	4 times per year	Elsevier
EEM https://eem25.pt/	International Conference on the European Energy Market	Yearly, next edition: 27-29 May 2025, Lisbon (Portugal)	EEM
SEST https://sest2024.polito.it/expression-of-interest-sest-2026/	International Conference on Smart Energy Systems and Technologies	Every 2 years, next edition in 2026	SEST
SmartGreens https://smartgreens.scitevents.org/	International Conference on Smart Cities and Green ICT Systems	Yearly, next edition: 2-3 April 2025, Porto (Portugal)	INSTICC
Energy Informatics https://energyinformatics.springeropen.com/	Open access journal on energy informatics in various scientific, technological, engineering and social fields to facilitate the global transition towards sustainable and resilient energy systems	Continuous (online)	Springer Nature

VI.7. Events / Workshops / Conferences

The BlueBird results will be actively promoted and presented on industry-oriented events, workshops and conferences. A number of potentially interesting events have been identified and shared with the consortium. This list will be continuously updated with new opportunities.

To spread information within the consortium on potentially relevant events, conferences, fairs, etc. we will (i) use the project's dissemination mailing list and (ii) present and discuss upcoming dissemination opportunities during the monthly project status calls and during the physical plenary meetings.

The table below gives an overview of the identified interesting events identified up to now.

Table 4 - Events

Event	Description	Date/ Periodicity/ Location	Benefit of attending
GreenTech Forum Brussels 2025 https://www.greentech-forum-brussels.com/	Expert-led panels, workshops, and keynote speeches addressing the latest trends and challenges in sustainable IT	June 17-18 2025	Presentation the ambitions of the BlueBird project and the Brussels pilot of WeSmart
EU Sustainable Energy Week (EUSEW) https://eusew.eu/	Policy Conference	Yearly, Brussels (Belgium)	Interesting for networking.
Enlit Europe https://www.enlit-europe.com/	Large exhibition and professional conference for energy companies.	Yearly, next edition: November 18-20 2025, Bilbao (Spain)	Interesting to present the project to a wide range of energy companies and professionals.
ChangeNOW - The largest event of solutions for the planet	Large conference on tech solutions for climate change	Yearly, next edition: 24-26 April 2025, Paris (France_	Interesting to join a panel or present thematic topics
World Sustainable Energy Days https://www.wsed.at/	Energy Efficiency Conference, Young Energy Researchers, Energy Efficiency Policy, Industrial Energy Transition. Possibility to participate in different ways: poster presentation, speaker	Yearly, next edition: 25-27 February, 2026, Wels (Austria).	Presenting results to the scientific and industrial EE and ET community.
C4E (Central & Eastern European Energy Efficiency) Forum https://c4eforum.net/	The go-to event for EPBD and EED implementation in CEE	Yearly in May; location changes each year	Try to join a panel to present thematic topics, specific use cases and solutions; interesting for networking.
Smart City Expo World Congress (SCEWC) https://www.smartcityexpo.com/	Public governments and Industry oriented congress about urban innovation in	Yearly in November, Barcelona (Spain).	Presenting specific use cases and

	cities and regions around the world.		solutions. Interesting for AMB pilot.
ECEEE annual policy seminar https://www.eceee.org/	Eceee (the European Council for an Energy Efficient Economy) is a membership-based non-profit association that generates and provides evidence-based knowledge and analysis of policies, and facilitates co-operation and networking	Yearly in November, Brussels (Belgium)	Try to join a panel to present thematic topics, specific use cases and solutions; interesting for networking.
E.DSO events (European Distribution System Operators) https://www.edsoforsmartgrids.eu/events/	Regular webinars and events on smart grids.	Several per year, typically in Brussels, Belgium	Interesting for networking and to present the project to DSOs.
smartEN summit https://smarten.eu/events/smarten-summit-2025-l-great-fleexpectations-the-flexible-demand-management-industry-for-a-decarbonised-and-competitive-europe/	Event organized by the European business association integrating consumer-driven solutions of the clean energy transition.	Yearly, next edition on May 20 2025 in Brussels (Belgium)	Interesting for networking and to present the project results to industry stakeholders
Sustainable Electric Power Generation under EU Conditions https://kee.fei.tuke.sk/?page_id=2297	Research workshop		Interesting to present the BlueBird goals and planned research activities

VII. PROJECT BRANDING

VII.1. Logo

For the branding of the project a logo was created, including a few variants (a horizontal, completely blue and completely white version). The logo will be used in all communication and dissemination actions, including the website, social media, flyers and posters, newsletters, presentations, deliverables, etc.

Figure 6. BlueBird logo

Figure 7. BlueBird logo variants (horizontal, blue, white)

VII.2. Templates

Templates have been created and distributed to all consortium partners for:

- Deliverables: a Word template, used for this deliverable, see also Figure 8. This template establishes a consistent style and format to ensure a professional presentation of the project results, and uniformity over all project deliverables.
- Presentation: a PowerPoint template for internal and external presentations, see Figure 9. This template ensures a consistent and professional visual identity in all project communications.

Figure 8. BlueBird deliverable template (Microsoft Word)

Figure 9. BlueBird presentation template (Microsoft PowerPoint)

VIII. MONITORING AND KPIs

The success of the communication and dissemination actions to promote the project results will be measured with a number of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), listed in the table below.

Table 5. Key Performance Indicators

KPI descripton	Target Audience	Target KPI Value	Lead Beneficiary	Supporting Beneficiaries
Posters and brochures	All TAs	3 (M2, M18, M36)	IMEC	All partners
Press releases or newsletters	All TAs	2 per year (6 in total)	IMEC, CIMNE	All partners
Project videos	All TAs	At least 3 (M2, M18, M36)	INETUM, IMEC	All partners
LinkedIn followers	TA1 / TA3 / TA4 / TA5	At least 500	IMEC	All partners
Website updates (blog posts, news updates, results, events, etc.)	All TAs	At least 1 per month	IMEC	All partners
Scientific publications in peer reviewed journals and proceedings of academic conferences and workshops	TA1 / TA3 / TA4 / TA5	At least 8	IMEC	All partners
White papers	TA1 / TA3 / TA4 / TA5	At least 4	IMEC	All partners
Participation in industry-oriented events and exhibitions	TA1 / TA4	At least 3 per year (= 9 in total)	IMEC	All partners
Public events organized by BlueBird in workshops at conferences	TA1 / TA3 / TA4 / TA5	2	IMEC	All partners
Stakeholder workshops	TA3	2 with at least 30 participants	BPIE	AIT

Final project conference in Brussels	TA3	1 (80+ participants)	CIMNE, IMEC	All partners
Outreach for surveys / interviews / workshop participation to relevant stakeholders	TA1 / TA2 / TA3 / TA4	10000+ end users, 100+ industry stakeholders, 50+ policy makers (over all pilots)	Pilot partners (KARNO, ENEA, WESMART, AMB, ENK, EWH, PSNC)	
Webinars to share pilot results with end users	TA1	6 in total (1 per pilot, but only 1 for the 2 ENEA pilots combined)	Pilot partners (KARNO, ENEA, WESMART, AMB, ENK, EWH, PSNC)	
Informing and engaging similar sites where the solution could be replicated	TA1 / TA2	15+ initiatives targeted	BPIE	AIT
# of national and EU policy makers and regulators reached by targeted outreach actions (bilateral meetings, stakeholder meetings, policy events)	TA3	150	BPIE	AIT
# of policy briefings, factsheets, recommendations	TA3	5	BPIE	AIT
# of multiplier organisations enrolled and engaged in stakeholder events	TA3	15	BPIE	AIT

IX. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable presents the activities planned to ensure a successful communication and dissemination of the BlueBird project results. It describes the objectives, the targeted audience and key stakeholders, the main outputs and material to disseminate along the project, as well as the channels which will be used to increase the visibility of the project. This to enhance the exploitation and take-up of BlueBird’s results. The deliverable provides an overview of the timing of public deliverables and milestones that will drive the communication actions and a monitoring strategy with KPIs to follow-up the effectiveness of the actions taken.

Communication and dissemination are a continuous process hence, all the activities described within this document will be carried out throughout the 36 months of BlueBird, with different focus depending on the stage of the project.

